

EU-DREAM

Effective Uptake of Digital Services to Repower European Consumers and Communities as Active Participants in Energy Transition and Markets

D3.1 Data Management and Security

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ACRONYMS

ACRONYMS	
AI	Artificial Intelligence
DLT	Distributed Ledger Technology
DLTI	Distributed Ledger Technology Interface
DT	Digital Twin
EU	European Union
IoT	Internet of Things
LL	Living Lab

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable presents the design and initial implementation of the **trusted data exchange layer** developed within Task 3.1 of the EU-DREAM project. The objective of this work is to ensure verifiable, tamper-proof, and efficient exchange of operational data across Digital Twins, energy services, and Living Labs, leveraging blockchain technology to build trust across modules and organizations.

The proposed architecture uses a permissioned blockchain (Hyperledger Besu) together with a Merkle-tree-based integrity mechanism implemented in the Go programming language. Rather than storing raw data on the blockchain, the system anchors compact integrity commitments (Merkle roots) on-chain and keeps full data off-chain, enabling lightweight yet verifiable proofs of integrity. This approach prevents the blockchain from becoming a bottleneck when handling high-frequency energy data.

A working prototype has been deployed and validated in a controlled environment. Early testing demonstrated that the system performs correctly in recording and checking data integrity. With QBFT (Quorum Byzantine Fault Tolerance) consensus, the system achieved a ~2 s block time and sustained ~200–300 transactions per second before performance degradation, indicating feasibility and areas for optimization.

The trusted exchange layer thus provides a transparent and interoperable foundation for EU-DREAM, enabling cross-module trust and auditability of shared datasets.

Future work will focus on improving scalability, reducing operational complexity, and supporting deployment in more distributed Living Lab scenarios.

Table of Contents

1. Introduction	8
2. Background and Objectives	9
a. Role of WP3 within the EU-DREAM project	9
b. Objectives of Task 3.1	9
3. Data Management and Security Models	11
a. DLT-based Trusted Data Exchange Layer	11
b. Security by design: encryption, access control, auditability	12
4. DLT Architecture and Merkle Tree	14
a. Private DLT architecture and motivation	15
b. DLT Interface	20
c. Merkle Tree mechanism for data integrity	20
d. Technical details: structure, hashing, proofs	22
e. Interaction between DLT, Digital Twin, and modules	25
f. Mechanism for data traceability and trust	27
g. Summary: key decisions and their impact	27
5. Technologies and Tools	29
a. Selected DLT platforms	29
b. Open-source tools used	30
6. Preliminary Implementation and Integration	34
a. Prototype and test environments	34
b. Initial functional verification	37
7. Results and Challenges	39
8. Conclusion	40
References	41

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1– EU-DREAM system architecture highlighting the DLT Interface and the blockchain-based Trusted Data Exchange within the overall platform.....	14
Figure 2 - QBFT consensus algorithm	17
Figure 3 - Data Hashing	23
Figure 4- Combining Hashes.....	23
Figure 5 - Data Validation.....	24
Figure 6 – Sequence Diagram of the Data Hashing workflow via DLTI	25
Figure 7 - Sequence Diagram of the Data Verification workflow via DLTI”	26
Figure 8- Architecture of the simulated blockchain environment (Hardhat-based)	34
Figure 9 - Architecture of the internal test network with validator nodes deployed on LINKS infrastructure	35
Figure 10 - Architecture of the mixed testbed with validator nodes distributed across Living Labs and LINKS, interconnected via VPN.....	36

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1 – Comparison of full on-chain storage versus Merkle-based anchoring approach in the EU-DREAM architecture.....	21
Table 2 – Evaluation of alternative blockchain platforms for Task 3.1.....	30
Table 3– Open-source tools and libraries used in the EU-DREAM trusted exchange layer.	31

1. Introduction

This deliverable presents the work carried out in Task 3.1 of the EU-DREAM project, which focuses on the design and development of a secure and trusted data exchange layer. The task is part of Work Package 3 (WP3), whose overarching objective is to ensure reliable, transparent, and compliant data handling mechanisms that can support Digital Twins, energy services, and Living Labs within the project ecosystem.

The document outlines the rationale for adopting Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLTs) and Merkle Tree structures to guarantee the integrity, immutability, and verifiability of exchanged information. It also describes the implemented security-by-design measures, addressing encryption, auditability, and GDPR compliance.

Furthermore, the deliverable details the architecture of the proposed DLT-based layer, the selected technologies and open-source tools, and the results of the preliminary prototyping and integration activities. Challenges encountered during the implementation and testing phases are also reported, together with an outlook on future refinements and integration with other project components.

The remainder of the document is structured as follows:

- **Section 0** provides the background and objectives of Task 3.1;
- **Section 0** introduces the data management and security models underpinning the design;
- **Section 4** explains the adopted Merkle Tree and DLT architecture;
- **Section 0** describes the technologies and tools used in the implementation;
- **Section 0** reports on preliminary implementation and integration activities;
- **Section 0** presents the main results and challenges identified;
- **Section 0** concludes the document.

2. Background and Objectives

a. Role of WP3 within the EU-DREAM project

Work Package 3 (WP3) plays a central role in the project by providing a cloud-based platform for energy-related data sharing, ensuring both security and interoperability across all technical modules. WP3 is responsible for building the Trusted Data Exchange Layer, acting as the backbone for the secure integration of data from different sources and domains. The main objectives of WP3 are:

1. Development of interoperable interfaces that enable seamless connections between heterogeneous data sources and the tools developed in other WPs.
2. Application of state-of-the-art data space principles, including Gaia-X, to guarantee interoperability, sovereignty, and trust, leveraging the outcomes of previous EU initiatives such as PROBONO (H2020).
3. Design of a federated data architecture, enabling cloud-based integration of distributed resources across multiple sites.
4. Incorporation of semantics and linked data infrastructures, ensuring machine-readability, interoperability, and facilitating the development of open APIs.

The innovative aspect of WP3 lies in the ability to federate data across sites using secure cloud technologies while embedding semantics to strengthen interoperability. Through these innovations, WP3 raises the technology readiness level (TRL) from 5 to 7, moving towards near-market integration of trusted data exchange solutions.

WP3 is closely integrated with other project activities:

- It leverages the requirements and system specifications from WP1.
- It ensures secure and trusted data exchange for the Digital Twins in WP2.
- It supports data management for energy services developed in WP4.
- It prepares integration and deployment in the Living Labs coordinated in WP7.

In this way, WP3 provides a horizontal and enabling layer that supports the project's ambition to create a secure and federated data ecosystem for energy.

b. Objectives of Task 3.1

Task 3.1 focuses on the design and implementation of the DLT-based Trusted Data Exchange Layer, as defined in the Grant Agreement. Its goal is to enable Digital Twins (DTs) to continuously access data while ensuring trust, integrity, and immutability of the information. By leveraging a permissioned distributed ledger (Hyperledger Besu¹), the task provides a foundation for trusted, transparent, and tamper-evident data exchange.

¹[Hyperledger Besu](#) is an enterprise-grade Ethereum client designed for private and consortium blockchains, supporting permissioned setups where only validator nodes across the consortium can participate in consensus and transaction validation.

This trusted layer acts as the backbone for secure interoperability across the EU-DREAM ecosystem, guaranteeing that data shared among modules and services cannot be modified without detection. In this way, Task 3.1 directly contributes to raising the technology readiness level (TRL) from 5 to 7 and establishes the operational basis for the higher-level functionalities addressed in WP2, WP4, and WP7.

3. Data Management and Security Models

a. DLT-based Trusted Data Exchange Layer

To ensure trust, integrity, and transparency in the EU-DREAM ecosystem, Task 3.1 has designed a Trusted Data Exchange Layer based on Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLTs). This layer acts as a secure backbone for the exchange of information between different modules (e.g., Digital Twins, energy services, Living Labs), guaranteeing that once data is shared, it cannot be altered without detection.

At the heart of this approach lies the concept of blockchain (Yu, 2022), the most prominent form of DLT. A blockchain is a distributed database that stores information in a sequence of blocks, each cryptographically linked to the previous one. This structure makes the ledger immutable, transparent, and secure: data cannot be retroactively modified, participants share a consistent version of the truth, and validation is achieved collectively through consensus rather than a single central authority.

The general characteristics of blockchain can be summarized as follows:

- **Decentralization:** the ledger is maintained across multiple nodes, removing the need for a central intermediary.
- **Immutability:** once data is added to the chain, it becomes computationally infeasible to modify it retroactively.
- **Transparency and auditability:** all transactions are visible to participants with the appropriate permissions, ensuring accountability.
- **Security through cryptography:** each block and transaction is digitally signed and chained, protecting data against unauthorized alterations.
- **Consensus mechanisms:** the network agrees on the validity of transactions using protocols that ensure consistency across distributed nodes.

Within EU-DREAM, these features underpin the Trusted Data Exchange Layer, where integrity and traceability of operations are guaranteed. Its main purposes are to provide:

- **Integrity of exchanged information:** once recorded, data is cryptographically secured and resistant to tampering.
- **Traceability of operations:** every transaction is permanently recorded on the ledger, ensuring that the history can always be verified.
- **Trust among stakeholders:** by reducing reliance on central intermediaries and relying on distributed consensus, the system fosters transparency and mutual confidence across actors.

The Trusted Data Exchange Layer is implemented through a DLTI (Distributed Ledger Technology Interface) that interacts with upstream modules. Depending on the use case, this interface can:

1. **Ingest data** provided by other modules, storing it in the DLT to ensure immutability and availability.
2. **Verify the integrity** of previously stored information by checking cryptographic proofs against the distributed ledger.

This dual functionality allows the EU-DREAM platform to cover both data recording and data validation scenarios, enabling flexible yet secure workflows. By embedding the DLT as a horizontal component, the project ensures that all technical modules can exchange information under a unified trust framework.

b. Security by design: encryption, access control, auditability

The architecture of the Trusted Data Exchange Layer in Task 3.1 has been conceived according to security-by-design principles, ensuring that protection mechanisms are embedded natively within the system rather than added as external features. This guarantees that data exchanged in EU-DREAM remains protected throughout its entire lifecycle.

Key features of this approach include:

- **Encryption:** Communication security is achieved through multiple layers. Validator nodes rely on **Ethereum's native peer-to-peer encryption (RLPx)**, which protects consensus and block propagation messages. In addition, all validator nodes and the DLTI middleware are interconnected through a **WireGuard-based VPN**. This private overlay network provides encrypted tunnels (**ChaCha20/Poly1305**) for communication between distributed components, ensuring that DLTI-to-blockchain interactions and node-to-node traffic are both protected against interception. Sensitive information stored off-chain. Complementing encryption, the system uses **Keccak-256 hashing** for constructing Merkle Trees, providing strong collision resistance and ensuring that any tampering with data is immediately detectable.
- **Access control:** As the platform relies on a **permissioned blockchain (Hyperledger Besu)**, all interactions are authenticated through cryptographic identities and fine-grained permissions, restricting operations to authorized actors only.
- **Auditability:** Every transaction anchored on the ledger creates a **tamper-evident audit trail**. This means that any attempt to modify or remove information immediately detectable, providing transparency and accountability for compliance with project and regulatory requirements.

This security architecture aligns with widely accepted cybersecurity and privacy best practices, including the principles of “**security by design**” and “**data protection by default**” as defined in Article 25 of the General Data Protection Regulation (European Union, 2016). By embedding encryption, controlled access, and verifiable auditability directly into the Trusted Data Exchange Layer, the system ensures that **security is a core architectural element** rather than an afterthought, supporting both technical robustness and regulatory preparedness.

As previously stated, the **EU-DREAM data management framework** has been designed to ensure full alignment with the **General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)** by embedding privacy and governance requirements directly into the architecture and operational workflows. In particular, the Trusted Data Exchange Layer developed in Task 3.1 supports the following principles:

- **Data minimization:** Only the evidence necessary to guarantee data integrity (e.g., hashes, identifiers) is anchored on the blockchain, while raw datasets remain in controlled databases. This reduces exposure and ensures that no unnecessary personal information is processed on-chain.
- **Accountability and auditability:** The immutable ledger provides a verifiable audit trail of all operations, making it possible to reconstruct data flows and guarantee compliance with project and legal requirements.
- **Privacy by design and by default:** Protection mechanisms (encryption, controlled access, minimization) are embedded from the earliest stages of the design process, so that GDPR compliance is an intrinsic property of the system rather than an afterthought.

This governance strategy ensures not only compliance with European legislation but also fosters **trust, transparency, and sovereignty** in the handling of energy-related data across the EU-DREAM ecosystem. The technical mechanisms supporting these principles, such as blockchain-based immutability and cryptographic proofs, are detailed in the following section.

4.DLT Architecture and Merkle Tree

Figure 1- EU-DREAM system architecture highlighting the DLT Interface and the blockchain-based Trusted Data Exchange within the overall platform.

Figure 1 shows the overall architecture of the EU-DREAM platform, which is structured in layers connecting external DLT data sources, core services, and advanced functionalities such as blockchain and Digital Twins.

The entire system integrates a variety of external data sources and consumers, including IoT devices (such as thermostats, hygrometers and smart meters), appliances, renewable energy systems, and market interfaces. This allows the platform to collect both real-time and historical information on user behavior, energy consumption and environmental conditions.

The collected information is then processed by the core platform services. These include the Platform Backend, which routes requests to the appropriate components; the NLP-based Intermediator, which enables non-technical users to interact with the system through natural language; and the Data Storage, which integrates semantic technologies with multiple databases optimized for different data types. Together, these components ensure usability, interoperability, and efficient management of heterogeneous datasets.

On top of this, the architecture includes two key elements: the DLT Interface and the Digital Twin environment. The DLT Interface provides integrity and security of all exchanged information, while the Digital Twin supports simulations and optimization tasks that enhance decision-making and energy efficiency.

Overall, this layered design highlights how EU-DREAM combines data collection, user interaction, secure exchange, and advanced analytics in a unified and trustworthy ecosystem.

a. Private DLT architecture and motivation

To guarantee trust, integrity, and controlled access in the EU-DREAM ecosystem, the project has adopted a private blockchain infrastructure as the foundation of the Trusted Data Exchange Layer. The rationale for using a permissioned Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) is threefold:

- **Governance:** Only authorized consortium partners can participate in consensus, ensuring that control remains within the EU-DREAM network.
- **Performance:** A permissioned blockchain achieves higher throughput and lower latency compared to public blockchains, which is crucial for near real-time validation of energy-related data.
- **Security and resilience:** By embedding consensus mechanisms at the core, the infrastructure complies with the project's security-by-design principles.

Beyond these generic advantages, DLTs are particularly well-suited to the EU-DREAM context. The platform requires trusted data exchange across multiple independent stakeholders (Living Labs, Digital Twins, and energy services) that do not necessarily trust each other but must collaborate on a common infrastructure. The immutable and auditable nature of the ledger ensures that data used for simulations, optimization, and energy-related services cannot be altered or disputed after publication. At the same time, the shared ledger provides transparent verification of operations, fostering trust among participants without relying on a central authority.

In short, blockchain is not used as a generic add-on, but as an enabler for trust, accountability, and traceability, which are prerequisites for deploying a consumer-centric energy platform operating across diverse technical and organizational boundaries.

The blockchain is implemented using Hyperledger Besu in permissioned mode, which makes it possible to explicitly define which nodes are allowed to participate in consensus and transaction validation. The network has been structured to include:

- **Validator nodes**, distributed across project partners and Living Labs (LLs), ensure transparency, decentralization, and resilience within the consortium.
- **A bootnode**, responsible for peer discovery and enabling new nodes to join the network, without directly participating in consensus or transaction validation.

Hyperledger Besu is an open-source Ethereum client designed for enterprise use (Hyperledger, s.d.) under the Linux Foundation's Hyperledger umbrella. It is Ethereum Virtual Machine (EVM) compatible, allowing the execution of smart contracts written in Solidity and the use of existing Ethereum tools (e.g., Hardhat, web3 libraries). This compatibility ensures a mature and well-supported development environment, while the permissioned configuration guarantees that control remains within the EU-DREAM consortium.

In its private setup, only validator nodes distributed across the consortium are allowed to participate in consensus and transaction validation. All interactions with the blockchain are handled exclusively through the DLTI. Higher-level components such as Digital Twins and energy-related applications communicate with the DLTI, which is in charge of interfacing directly with the blockchain through standard APIs, ensuring secure and policy-compliant access to the ledger.

Consensus is based on **QBFT² (Quorum Byzantine Fault Tolerance)**, an algorithm specifically optimized for consortium-oriented networks. QBFT ensures:

- Deterministic and low-latency block finality, avoiding the probabilistic confirmation delays typical of public blockchains.
- Resilience against malicious behavior, tolerating up to f faulty nodes out of $3f + 1$.
- Predictable and stable performance, suitable for continuous data validation in near real-time.

²<https://besu.hyperledger.org/private-networks/how-to/configure/consensus/qbft/>

Below is a diagram to better explain how the consensus algorithm works.

Figure 2 - QBFT consensus algorithm

This configuration defines:

- **chainId**: unique integer number identifier of the network;
- **berlinBlock**: block number at which the *Berlin* hard fork is activated (here 0, meaning from the beginning).
- **qbft**: parameters for the Quorum Byzantine Fault Tolerance (QBFT) consensus algorithm.
 - **blockperiodseconds**: time interval (in seconds) between consecutive blocks (2s).
 - **epochlength**: number of blocks after which validators refresh their certificates (30,000).
 - **requesttimeoutseconds**: timeout for consensus requests (4s).
- **nonce**: unique value used to distinguish the network during initialization.
- **timestamp**: initial timestamp of the chain.
- **gasLimit**: maximum gas allowed per block, defining how many transactions can be included.
- **difficulty**: parameter from Proof of Work networks (kept for compatibility, not relevant in QBFT).
- **mixHash**: fixed value required for block validity in Ethereum, unused in QBFT, but mandatory.
- **coinbase**: default miner/beneficiary address (set to zero in QBFT).
- **alloc**: pre-allocated balances to assign to a specific address.
- **extraData**: contains the list of authorized validator addresses and additional metadata for consensus.

The configuration adopted in Task 3.1 foresees a permissioned Hyperledger Besu network composed of four validator nodes:

- Three nodes hosted within the project's Living Labs (Denmark, Greece, and Ireland),
- One node hosted at LINKS.

To ensure secure and reliable communication across geographically distributed infrastructures, the validator nodes are interconnected through a **WireGuard-based Virtual Private Network (VPN)**, which is extremely simple, fast, and modern, and utilizes state-of-the-art cryptography (WireGuard). This choice simplifies node discovery, enforces encrypted communication channels, and provides an additional layer of access control, guaranteeing that only authorized consortium members can exchange consensus messages. The VPN also abstracts network heterogeneity across sites, making the deployment more robust and easier to manage.

By distributing validator nodes across three Living Labs and LINKS, and securing their interaction via VPN, the architecture achieves geographic decentralization, resilience, and governance alignment with the project's objectives. This setup provides a realistic foundation for testing interoperability and trust mechanisms under real-world conditions while maintaining the consortium's control over participation and security.

b. DLT Interface

To ensure secure and consistent interaction with the blockchain, all transactions in EU-DREAM are mediated through a dedicated middleware component called the Distributed Ledger Technologies Interface (DLTI).

The DLTI acts as the sole gateway between application-level modules (e.g., Digital Twins, databases, energy services) and the permissioned blockchain, *as illustrated in Figure 1*. Its main roles are:

- **Abstraction of blockchain complexity:** By providing a clean API, the DLTI shields upstream modules from the technical details of blockchain protocols, enabling secure integration without requiring direct blockchain expertise.
- **Controlled and federated access:** Validator nodes, distributed across Living Labs and project partners, maintain the shared, tamper-proof ledger. A limited number of DLTI instances operated by the consortium mediate all application-level interactions with the blockchain, ensuring secure access control while supporting a federated, resilient architecture aligned with diverse European regulatory contexts.
- **Data anchoring:** The DLTI preprocesses incoming data by constructing a Merkle tree and deriving the root hash. Only the root and a reference identifier are submitted to the blockchain, while the full dataset and its Merkle structure remain securely stored off-chain. This design ensures integrity and non-repudiation without overloading the ledger, in line with data minimization and privacy principles.
- **Data verification:** Using the stored Merkle root, the DLTI enables later verification that any given data item was included in the original dataset anchored on-chain. This ensures transparency, auditability, and trust in the integrity of the exchanged information.

c. Merkle Tree mechanism for data integrity

Ensuring the integrity and consistency of data is a key requirement for the Trusted Data Exchange Layer. In a distributed environment such as the one envisioned in EU-DREAM, participants must be able to verify that the exchanged information has not been tampered with, even when operating across multiple systems and infrastructures.

To address this challenge, architecture adopts the Merkle Tree data structure through the implementation of smart contract logic leveraging the blockchain layer. A Merkle Tree is a hierarchical hashing scheme that allows large datasets to be represented through a single cryptographic value (the Merkle Root). Each element in the dataset is hashed, and these hashes are recursively combined until the root is obtained.

The motivation for using Merkle Trees is threefold:

- **Efficient verification:** instead of accessing and validating the entire dataset, a user only needs a small number of hashes (a Merkle proof) to confirm the integrity of a specific piece of data.
- **Tamper detection:** any unauthorized modification in the dataset propagates up to the Merkle Root, making alterations immediately detectable.
- **Scalability:** the approach significantly reduces computation and communication overhead, enabling secure verification even when dealing with large amounts of data across distributed systems.

An additional benefit of this mechanism is its ability to avoid turning the blockchain into a bottleneck. High-frequency data streams, such as those produced by sensors and monitoring equipment, would be impractical to store directly on-chain due to latency and scalability constraints. Instead, only lightweight cryptographic commitments (Merkle Roots) are recorded on the ledger, while full datasets are handled off-chain. This approach guarantees both verifiability and high throughput.

As shown in *Table 1*, the Merkle-based anchoring strategy adopted in EU-DREAM provides significant advantages compared to traditional on-chain storage, particularly in terms of scalability, performance, and privacy preservation.

Table 1 - Comparison of full on-chain storage versus Merkle-based anchoring approach in the EU-DREAM architecture.

Aspect	Full On-Chain Data	Merklee Root + Off-Chain DB
GDPR compliance	✗ Impossible to delete data (violates right to erasure)	☑ Personal data can be deleted off-chain
Scalability	✗ Poor (slow reads/writes, high cost per entry)	☑ High scalability with DB and lightweight on-chain root
Performance	✗ Slow (full chain traversal, limited throughput)	☑ Fast (DB for access, Merkle proof for integrity)
Data integrity	☑ Guaranteed	☑ Guaranteed via cryptographic root
Privacy	✗ Risk of exposing sensitive data	☑ Data remains private off-chain

In addition to the conceptual advantages, the project opted to use the **Go programming language** for implementing the Merkle Tree component. Go was selected because it offers:

- **Native integration** with the blockchain client and middleware, avoiding cross-language dependencies and ensuring lightweight execution.
- **High performance and efficiency**, thanks to its concurrency model and memory management, well suited for handling high-frequency data streams.
- **Simplicity and maintainability**, as its minimalistic syntax reduces code complexity and makes the library easier to audit and extend.
- **Open availability**, since the resulting library could be released under an open-source license for reuse in other contexts.

While [OpenZeppelin](#) provides widely adopted and audited implementations of Merkle Tree verification in Solidity, specifically through the *MerkleProof.sol* contract used to validate Merkle proofs on-chain (OpenZeppelin, s.d.), there was no suitable library available in the Go language for computing Merkle Trees off-chain. For this reason, we developed a custom Go-based implementation of Merkle Trees, inspired by OpenZeppelin's structure and logic, but fully rewritten to support the needs of EU-DREAM's Trusted Data Exchange Layer.

This implementation is used to compute the Merkle Root and generate valid proofs before anchoring them on the blockchain. Our smart contracts directly integrate OpenZeppelin's Solidity libraries for proof verification, ensuring compatibility with Ethereum standards. The custom Go library complements this by enabling high-performance off-chain computation of the tree. The implementation is available publicly at: <https://github.com/AleMoz97/merkle-tree-go>

d. Technical details: structure, hashing, proofs

As previously described, the integrity of exchanged information is ensured through the use of a Merkle Tree, a cryptographic structure that allows large datasets to be represented and verified through a single digest, known as the Merkle Root. This mechanism guarantees that any alteration to the data, even a single bit, becomes immediately detectable. To illustrate its functioning, the process can be divided into three steps, shown in the figures below.

Step 1 – Data hashing

Figure 3 - Data Hashing

Each element of the dataset is first processed with the Keccak-256 hashing function, the standard used in Ethereum-compatible blockchains, so also in Hyperledger Besu. This produces a fixed-length cryptographic digest that uniquely represents the input. Even the smallest change in the input leads to a completely different hash, a property that ensures immutability and tamper evidence. These initial hashes form the *leaves* of the Merkle Tree and represent the secure, low-level building blocks of the structure. By reducing raw data to hashes, the system ensures both privacy and efficiency, since only these compact digests are manipulated in subsequent steps.

Step 2 – Combining hashes

Figure 4- Combining Hashes

The leaf hashes are then combined in pairs and hashed again, forming the intermediate nodes of the tree. This operation is repeated recursively until only one hash remains at the top, known as the Merkle Root. The root acts as a compact cryptographic fingerprint of the entire dataset. Its value depends on all underlying data: any modification at the leaf level propagates upwards, producing a different root. In practice, this means that instead of storing or verifying a large dataset directly, the system only needs to store the root on the blockchain. This drastically reduces the amount of information recorded on-chain, while still preserving the ability to verify the integrity of the whole dataset.

Step 3 – Data validation through Merkle Proofs

Needed	To validate, we need all of these values
Computed	We can compute these, given the values above
Known	This is the information we need to store

Figure 5 - Data Validation

When a participant needs to verify that a given item is part of a dataset, the system generates a Merkle Proof. This proof consists of the minimal set of sibling hashes needed to recompute the path from the leaf to the root. The verifier recomputes each step using Keccak-256 until the root is reconstructed and then compares it with the one stored on-chain. If the values match, the inclusion of the item is confirmed; if not, tampering is immediately detected. The efficiency of this process is remarkable: the size of the proof grows only logarithmically with the number of data items, meaning that even in very large datasets, verification remains lightweight. For example, to validate an element in a dataset of one million entries, only about 20 hashes are needed.

By following these steps, the Trusted Data Exchange Layer developed in Task 3.1 ensures tamper-proof verification with minimal overhead. Data remains stored off-chain in the appropriate repositories, while only the Merkle Root is anchored on the blockchain. This hybrid approach guarantees scalability and GDPR compliance, since personal or high-frequency data never needs to be directly stored on-chain, while at the same time ensuring full verifiability and trust across consortium partners.

e. Interaction between DLT, Digital Twin, and modules

The interaction between the Digital Twins and the DLT layer follows a two-phase workflow designed to guarantee both integrity and the verifiability of exchanged information, while ensuring smooth integration with the wider EU-DREAM ecosystem.

Phase 1 – Data hashing

Figure 6 – Sequence Diagram of the Data Hashing workflow via DLT

Figure 6 illustrates the sequence of interactions involved in the data hashing and anchoring process. Sensors deployed in the Living Labs periodically send measurements to the Data Platform. Upon reception, the Data Platform stores the records and assigns a unique set identifier (*setOfDataId*), ensuring that each batch can be traced unambiguously. The set of data, together with its identifier, is then forwarded to the DLTI.

At this stage, the DLTI is responsible for computing the Merkle Tree of the set of data. From this structure, only the Merkle Root is anchored on the permissioned blockchain (Hyperledger Besu), along with a set identifier (*setOfDataId*, root). The blockchain responds with a transaction acknowledgment, guaranteeing immutability and verifiability of the commitment. Finally, the DLTI generates the Merkle Proofs associated with the set of data and returns them to the Data Platform, where both the raw data and proofs are preserved for future verification.

Phase 2 – Data Verification

Figure 7 - Sequence Diagram of the Data Verification workflow via DLTI

The second phase, as illustrated in Figure 7, describes the sequence used to verify a dataset. When a Digital Twin needs to run a simulation, it relies on a Data Handler to retrieve the required historical inputs. The Data Handler queries the Data Platform, requesting the set of data and its associated Merkle proofs by referencing the *setOfDataId*.

The Data Platform responds with the raw set of data and the corresponding proofs. The Data Handler then engages the DLTI to validate integrity. The DLTI queries the blockchain (Besu) to retrieve the authoritative Merkle Root anchored for the given *set of DataId*.

Using the proofs provided by the Data Platform, the DLTI recomputes the hash path from the requested item up to the root. If the recomputed value matches the on-chain root, the integrity of the set of data is confirmed. Otherwise, the DLTI raises an anomaly, informing the Digital Twin that the requested inputs cannot be cryptographically verified.

Through this mechanism, the architecture guarantees tamper-evident validation of any set of data, while ensuring that heavy data flows remain off-chain and only integrity commitments are maintained in the distributed ledger.

f. Mechanism for data traceability and trust

In the EU-DREAM architecture, data traceability is ensured by anchoring each dataset batch to the blockchain through a unique identifier and its corresponding Merkle Root. This design guarantees that the state of the dataset at the time of submission is permanently recorded and cannot be altered without detection.

Rather than monitoring individual user actions, the system focuses on dataset-level commitments, providing a transparent and auditable history of the information exchanged. Any Digital Twin or module can validate the integrity of the data it consumes through Merkle proofs, ensuring that computations and services always rely on tamper-evident inputs.

This approach provides three key assurances:

- Traceability: every dataset batch is linked to a verifiable reference in the ledger;
- Integrity: unauthorized modifications are immediately detectable;
- Trustworthiness: modules and stakeholders operate only on data that can be cryptographically validated.

By adopting dataset-level anchoring instead of fine-grained logging of user actions, the framework strikes a balance between transparency and efficiency: it enables auditability and accountability without overburdening the system or compromising privacy.

g. Summary: key decisions and their impact

EU-DREAM secures data exchange with a permissioned Hyperledger Besu network using QBFT, distributing validator nodes across partners and interconnecting them via a WireGuard VPN for resilient, encrypted operations. All interactions pass through the DLTI middleware, which abstracts blockchain complexity and enforces controlled access. Instead of storing raw data on-chain, the platform anchors Merkle roots while keeping full datasets off-chain, combining verifiability with GDPR-friendly data minimization and high throughput.

This design delivers:

- Trust through tamper-evident commitments and auditable verification;
- Security via permissioned consensus, segregated roles and encrypted transport;
- Interoperability by exposing clean APIs that let Digital Twins and services hash, anchor, and later verify data without blockchain expertise.

In short, the architecture couples enterprise-grade robustness with practical performance for real-world energy scenarios.

5. Technologies and Tools

a. Selected DLT platforms

The choice of **Hyperledger Besu** is not arbitrary; it was guided by project-specific requirements:

- **Consortium governance:** Besu natively supports permissioned consensus, allowing a predefined set of validators to secure the ledger. This ensures controlled participation and aligns with the governance model of an EU-funded consortium.
- **Ecosystem compatibility:** As an Ethereum-compatible client, Besu allows the reuse of widely adopted smart contract standards (ERC20, ERC721), tools, and developer libraries, reducing integration effort and ensuring future extensibility.
- **Privacy and security:** The platform provides strong cryptographic primitives (Keccak-256 hashing) and supports private transactions and fine-grained access control features essential for handling sensitive energy data.
- **Maturity and openness:** Maintained under the Hyperledger Foundation, Besu benefits from an active developer community, open-source transparency, and enterprise-grade support. This ensures long-term sustainability beyond the project lifetime.

To support this decision, different Distributed Ledger Technologies were compared against the project's requirements. *Table 2 – Evaluation of alternative blockchain platforms for Task 3.1* summarizes the main alternatives considered and highlights the reasons why Hyperledger Besu was selected as the most suitable option.

Table 2 – Evaluation of alternative blockchain platforms for Task 3.1

Blockchain Platform	Key Features	Pros	Cons	Relevance for Task 3.1
Ethereum (public)	Open, public PoW/PoS network, global ecosystem	Large ecosystem, high decentralization, wide tooling support	High latency, transaction costs, not suitable for sensitive data	✘ Unsuitable for consortium use due to a lack of permissioning and GDPR risks
Hyperledger Fabric	Permissioned DLT, modular architecture, not EVM-compatible	Rich in enterprise features, strong access control, modular consensus	Not EVM-compatible, requires custom chaincode, limited reuse of Ethereum standards	⚠ Good for permissioned governance, but poor compatibility with existing Ethereum smart contracts and tools
Quorum	Ethereum fork for enterprise use, supports Raft/IBFT consensus	EVM-compatible, designed for private/permissioned setups	Slower community adoption after ConsenSys shift to Besu, less Active development	⚠ Technically suitable, but weaker long-term sustainability
Hyperledger Besu	Enterprise-grade Ethereum client (EVM-compatible), supports public and private modes	EVM-compatible, supports QBFT consensus, strong community, enterprise-ready, long-term sustainability	Slightly more complex setup than Fabric	✔ Best fit: combines Ethereum ecosystem compatibility with permissioned governance and long-term sustainability

As shown in *Table 2 – Evaluation of alternative blockchain platforms for Task 3.1*, Hyperledger Besu combines Ethereum compatibility, permissioned governance, and long-term sustainability, making it the most appropriate choice for Task 3.1 and the EU-DREAM Trusted Data Exchange Layer.

b. Open-source tools used

The development of the DLT-based trusted exchange layer leverages a set of open-source tools and libraries. Table 3 summarizes the main components and their role in the project.

Table 3- Open-source tools and libraries used in the EU-DREAM trusted exchange layer.

Tool / Library	Role
Hyperledger Besu	Ethereum-based client, the backbone of the permissioned blockchain network.
Go-Ethereum (Geth)	Reference implementation for low-level blockchain and cryptographic functions.
Keccak-256	Standard hashing function ensuring collision resistance and immutability.
Hardhat	Development framework for compiling, testing, and deploying smart contracts.
Go-Ethereum (Geth)	Reference implementation used for low-level blockchain and cryptographic functions, as well as programmatic interaction with contracts and transactions.
MQTT	Lightweight publish/subscribe protocol for real-time data collection.
WireGuard-based Virtual Private Network (VPN)	Secure tunneling protocol ensuring encrypted and low-latency communication between distributed nodes.
Docker & Docker Compose	Containerization and orchestration of blockchain nodes and related services.

Among the tools and libraries listed in Table 3, some require a more detailed explanation.

Keccak-256 is the hashing algorithm used as the standard within Ethereum-based networks. It produces a 256-bit digest that guarantees collision resistance (two different inputs cannot generate the same output) and immutability (any change in the input drastically alters the hash). In the Task 3.1 context, Keccak-256 is used to secure transactions, generate cryptographic identifiers, and support the Merkle Tree construction for proof validation.

[Hardhat](#) is a modern development framework for Ethereum-compatible blockchains, designed to support the full lifecycle of smart contract creation. Unlike older tools such as Truffle or Ganache, Hardhat combines compilation, testing, deployment, and debugging into a single, extensible environment (Nomic Foundation, s.d.).

At its core, Hardhat provides a local Ethereum network (Hardhat Network) that simulates a blockchain in memory. This feature allows developers to execute transactions instantly, mine blocks automatically, and run tests at high speed. The network also supports advanced debugging tools, such as detailed Solidity stack traces and the possibility to log outputs directly from within smart contracts. These capabilities significantly reduce the time required to identify and fix errors.

The framework is built around a task runner and plugin system, which makes it highly adaptable. Common tasks, such as contract compilation or deployment, can be automated and extended through official and community plugins, including integrations with OpenZeppelin, ethers.js, and testing libraries. Hardhat also supports multiple Solidity compiler versions, ensuring compatibility with diverse projects.

In practice, Hardhat enables a smooth workflow: contracts are written in Solidity, compiled with a single command, tested locally on the Hardhat Network, and then deployed either to public networks or to private infrastructures such as Hyperledger Besu in permissioned mode. This guarantees consistency across environments, from early prototyping to production deployments.

[Go-Ethereum](#) (Ethereum Foundation, s.d.) is one of the official implementations of the Ethereum protocol, written in Go. In EU-DREAM, it serves a dual role: on the one hand, it provides low-level blockchain and cryptographic functions that complement Hyperledger Besu; on the other hand, it enables programmatic interaction with contracts and transactions through its Go APIs. This makes it possible to integrate the DLT Interface directly into the Go-based middleware, without relying on external JavaScript libraries such as ethers.js.

MQTT (Message Queuing Telemetry Transport) is a lightweight, publish/subscribe communication protocol designed for simplicity, bandwidth efficiency, and resilience to unreliable networks. It is widely used in IoT scenarios, where constrained devices and distributed infrastructures require reliable and asynchronous communication.

Within Task 3.1, MQTT is adopted by the DLTI to manage different types of interactions with the Data Platform through dedicated topics. High-frequency data streams are published on specific topics to be collected and prepared for anchoring on the blockchain. Separate topics are used to transmit the corresponding Merkle proofs, as well as to receive the data that must be verified during integrity checks. This topic-based separation ensures that ingestion, proof management, and verification requests remain logically distinct while sharing the same lightweight, scalable communication layer.

By leveraging MQTT in this way, the architecture guarantees efficient and reliable data exchange with the blockchain layer, while supporting scalability and operation even under limited bandwidth or intermittent connectivity conditions.

WireGuard VPN is a modern, open-source Virtual Private Network protocol designed to be lightweight, fast, and highly secure. Compared to traditional VPN solutions, it has a minimal codebase, which enhances auditability and reduces attack surfaces. WireGuard relies on state-of-the-art cryptographic primitives (Curve25519 for key exchange, ChaCha20 for encryption, Poly1305 for authentication), ensuring strong protection of data in transit while maintaining low latency and high performance. Its simplicity and efficiency have made it widely adopted in distributed systems where secure, continuous connectivity is required.

Within EU-DREAM, a WireGuard-based VPN is used to securely connect the validator nodes deployed across the Living Labs and DLTI. This private overlay network ensures encrypted communication between geographically distributed sites, enabling all validators to participate reliably in the permissioned blockchain consensus while preserving the confidentiality and integrity of the exchanged data.

[Docker](#) and Docker Compose are used to containerize the blockchain infrastructure and orchestrate the execution of multiple nodes. This ensures that validator and participant nodes can be deployed reliably and reproducibly across different environments, facilitating both development and production setups.

By relying on open-source components with active community support, the EU-DREAM architecture ensures transparency, replicability, and long-term sustainability, while maintaining interoperability with the broader Ethereum ecosystem.

6. Preliminary Implementation and Integration

a. Prototype and test environments

To validate the progressive development of the DLT-based trusted data exchange layer, three main test environments have been set up, moving gradually from fully controlled conditions to mixed deployments with Living Labs.

1) Simulated blockchain environment (Hardhat-based)

Figure 8- Architecture of the simulated blockchain environment (Hardhat-based)

The first testing environment, shown in Figure 8, relied on **Hardhat**, a development framework that provides a simulated Ethereum-compatible blockchain running entirely on local developer machines. In this setup, no real validator nodes were required: the blockchain, accounts, and transactions were emulated in memory. The goal of this phase was to implement and validate the preliminary prototype of the DLTI, developed in Go, under controlled and low-cost conditions. The DLTI was connected to the Hardhat network to test two fundamental workflows:

- **Data Hashing:** incoming datasets were processed to build Merkle Trees, and only the resulting Merkle Root was submitted to the simulated blockchain through smart contracts.
- **Data Verification:** the DLTI verified datasets by reconstructing Merkle proofs and comparing the recomputed root against the one anchored on the Hardhat chain.
- **Smart Contract test:** verifying that the smart contract logic behaves correctly.

This environment allowed rapid prototyping and high-speed iterations, since contracts could be deployed and redeployed instantly, with full debugging support. Smart contracts were executed locally within Hardhat, ensuring deterministic outcomes and making it possible to quickly identify and correct design issues.

By using this simulated blockchain, the consortium was able to validate the end-to-end anchoring and verification mechanisms of the Trusted Data Exchange Layer before moving to more complex and resource-intensive deployments.

2) Internal test network (validator nodes on LINKS infrastructure)

Figure 9 - Architecture of the internal test network with validator nodes deployed on LINKS infrastructure

The second phase, shown in Figure 9, moved from a fully simulated environment to a realistic blockchain deployment hosted within the **LINKS** infrastructure. In this configuration, a private network of **Hyperledger Besu** validator nodes was orchestrated using Docker containers, with an additional bootnode supporting peer discovery. Each validator was configured to also act as an **RPC** node, enabling the submission of transactions and queries while simultaneously participating in the QBFT consensus. To test the DLT Interface (DLTI) in production-like conditions, a **Stub Database** and a **Digital Twin Emulator** were connected as external components. These emulated modules allowed controlled validation of data hashing and verification workflows without requiring the integration of real services at this stage. Communication between these components and the DLTI was managed via the **MQTT protocol**, ensuring compatibility with the data ingestion mechanisms envisioned for the Living Labs.

The DLTI, implemented in Go, was connected to blockchain nodes via the **Go-Ethereum (Geth)** client libraries. Its role remained to:

- compute Merkle Trees over incoming datasets,
- anchor Merkle Roots and metadata on-chain,
- retrieve and verify proofs against the blockchain state.

This test environment allowed LINKS to evaluate network stability, test different consensus parameters, and validate the integration of the Go-based Merkle Tree library under realistic latency and resource constraints. Unlike the simulated Hardhat setup, this deployment reproduced conditions closer to a production environment, enabling end-to-end validation of the Trusted Data Exchange Layer with full node orchestration and persistent blockchain state.

3) Mixed test network (LINKS and Living Labs nodes)

Figure 10 - Architecture of the mixed testbed with validator nodes distributed across Living Labs and LINKS, interconnected via VPN.

The third testing environment, shown in Figure 10, extended the blockchain deployment beyond the LINKS infrastructure by including validator nodes hosted at three **Living Labs** (Denmark, Greece, and Ireland). Together with the validator operated by LINKS, this configuration resulted in a distributed network of four validators interconnected through a **WireGuard VPN**. The VPN ensured encrypted communication, simplified peer discovery, and provided secure connectivity across geographically dispersed infrastructures.

In this setup, the **DLTI** remained hosted at LINKS, continuing to perform data hashing, Merkle Tree construction, and verification operations. It was connected to a Stub Database and a Digital Twin Emulator for controlled testing, while simultaneously interacting with the distributed validator nodes to anchor and verify data on-chain. Each validator was configured as a **Validator/RPC** node, enabling it to both participate in the QBFT consensus and expose RPC endpoints for transaction submission and state queries. The **bootnode** was also kept within the LINKS infrastructure, providing a stable entry point for network peers. By distributing validator nodes across different countries and infrastructures, the mixed testbed introduced realistic network variability (latency, bandwidth fluctuations) and multi-party governance conditions. This allowed the consortium to validate:

- the resilience of the **QBFT** consensus under geographically distributed conditions,
- the effectiveness of access control policies in a multi-operator environment,
- the ability of the **DLTI** to anchor and verify data across organizational boundaries.

This stage represented a key milestone towards real-world validation, demonstrating that the Trusted Data Exchange Layer can scale beyond a single organization and operate reliably across distributed partners while preserving data integrity and trust.

These environments confirmed that the Trusted Data Exchange Layer can anchor and verify data reliably, operate under realistic network conditions, and scale across multiple organizations, thereby providing a solid foundation for its integration into real-world Living Lab scenarios, while also demonstrating its readiness for long-term sustainability and cross-domain adoption.

b. Initial functional verification

Initial functional verification activities were carried out to ensure that the trusted data exchange layer operated correctly and interacted as expected with the other project components. The tests concentrated on three main aspects:

- **Data anchoring:** validating that data batches could be correctly processed through the Merkle Tree, with roots consistently and reliably committed to the blockchain.
- **Proof generation and validation:** confirmation that Merkle proofs were properly generated and could be successfully used by verifiers (e.g., Digital Twins) to check dataset integrity against the blockchain-anchored root.
- **Interfacing with the DLT network:** assessment of the communication between the DLT Interface and the underlying permissioned blockchain, ensuring that transactions were correctly formatted, submitted, and recorded.

The results of these tests confirmed that the mechanisms implemented by the exchange layer effectively guarantee data integrity, immutability, and verifiability. Furthermore, controlled experiments in the prototype environment demonstrated successful end-to-end interoperability: Digital Twins were able to request datasets, receive the corresponding Merkle proofs, and validate their consistency in real time.

This initial verification step provides confidence in the robustness of the design and establishes the technical readiness of the trusted data exchange layer for integration into the wider EU-DREAM architecture.

7. Results and Challenges

The activities conducted in Task 3.1 produced a set of concrete outcomes that lay the foundations for the trusted data exchange layer:

- **Architecture definition:** a clear design of the trusted exchange layer was established, specifying its role and interactions with Digital Twins (WP2), energy services (WP4), and Living Labs (WP7).
- **Prototype implementation:** a first working prototype was delivered, integrating a custom Merkle Tree library (developed in Go) with the Hyperledger Besu permissioned blockchain.
- **Functional validation:** core functionalities were verified, including data anchoring, proof generation, and integrity checks based on Merkle proofs.
- **Controlled testing environment:** a private network was deployed to experiment with consensus parameters, block period configuration, and validator node management.

These experiments demonstrated the capability of the system to consistently generate blocks every two seconds under QBFT consensus. Preliminary stress tests confirmed that the network can sustain up to 200–300 transactions per second in controlled conditions; beyond this threshold, latency increases and validator synchronization becomes less reliable.

Alongside these results, several challenges were identified:

- **Interoperability:** seamless integration with external modules required iterative adaptations of the data exchange interfaces.
- **Scalability:** while satisfactory in laboratory settings, further optimization will be necessary to handle larger transaction volumes in operational environments.
- **Operational complexity:** validator node management and private network maintenance introduce non-negligible administrative overhead, especially in distributed Living Lab deployments.

8. Conclusion

This deliverable reported on the activities carried out in Task 3.1, focusing on the design and preliminary implementation of a secure and trusted data exchange layer for the EU-DREAM project. A DLT-based approach, supported by Merkle Tree structures, was adopted to ensure the integrity, immutability, and verifiability of exchanged information while supporting GDPR compliance and security-by-design principles.

The main achievements include the definition of the architectural framework, the implementation of a first prototype in a controlled environment, and the demonstration of basic interoperability with Digital Twins, energy services, and Living Labs. Initial functional verification confirmed the feasibility of the proposed approach.

Several challenges were identified, such as scalability constraints, interoperability with heterogeneous systems, and the need to balance transparency with data privacy. These aspects will guide the refinement of the architecture and the evolution of the implementation in future phases of the project.

Overall, the work carried out in Task 3.1 establishes a solid foundation for trusted data management and exchange across the EU-DREAM ecosystem, enabling secure integration of distributed components and supporting the project's long-term objectives.

Future work will focus on consolidating the current Living Lab deployments by integrating the Trusted Data Exchange Layer more tightly into the overall EU-DREAM architecture, improving blockchain throughput, and extending interoperability with heterogeneous systems. These enhancements will ensure both scalability and robustness in real-world conditions.

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